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20 lines

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Darkest Hour

Nights are always gloomy, and I can't fall asleep,
Drowned in my own thoughts; didn't know they're that deep.
Tears are running fast, mind's about to swell,
Lost at the bottom of my subconscious hell.

The feeling of being chased is killing me inside,
By nightmarish shadows; there's nowhere I can hide
Save me from the ghosts watching from afar
Listen as I scream behind this eerie bar.

Imprisoned for so long in this vast wilderness
Wandering all alone with constant bitterness
Demons are screeching, no such thing as bliss
Now fading slowly, where can I find peace?

My mind has created an inescapable maze
Decorated by fear, anxiety, and haze
Disturbing voices coming from the walls nearby
Do whispers constantly, pushing me to die.

Darkness, now blurry, is quietly spreading.
In a one-time blink is merciless killing.
Now I'm lost in my mind; where can I find the light?
Escape is what I want — will I survive tonight?

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